

CONDENSATION OF DINITROCHLOROTOLUENES WITH *p*-NITROSODIMETHYLANILINE.

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Sachs and Kempf (*Ber.*, 1902, 85, 1224) prepared 2:4 dinitrobenzaldehyde and 2:4:6-trinitrobenzaldehyde by heating 2:4-dinitrotoluene and 2:4:6-trinitrotoluene with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline in the presence of alcohol and sodium carbonate and hydrolysing the products obtained with 2*N*-nitric acid. 2:4-Dinitro-5-chlorobenzaldehyde, 3:5-dinitro-4-chlorobenzaldehyde and 3:5-dinitro-2-chlorobenzaldehyde have now been prepared by heating the corresponding toluene hydrocarbons with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline in the presence of alcohol and sodium carbonate and hydrolysing the product so formed with 2*N*-nitric acid.

2:4-Dinitro-5-chlorobenzaldehyde was obtained as yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 150-52°; phenylhydrazone, m.p. 217°; oxime, m.p. above 280°.

3:5-Dinitro-4-chlorobenzaldehyde was obtained as yellow crystals from alcohol, m.p. 79-80°; phenylhydrazone, m.p. 109°; benzylideneaniline, m.p. 108°; oxime, m.p. above 290°.

3:5-Dinitro-2-chlorobenzaldehyde was obtained as yellow crystals from alcohol, m.p. 78°; oxime, m.p. above 290°, benzylideneaniline, m.p. 138°.

The corresponding benzoic and cinnamic acids have been prepared from these aldehydes. They have also been reduced and the derivatives of these reduction products have been prepared.

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